

BRIGADA PAGBASA IMPLEMENTATION AND READING ADVANCEMENT IN BAGANGA SOUTH DISTRICT

HAZEL MAE B. GALLARDO

Abstract. This descriptive-correlational research study explores the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa, a reading initiative, and its relationship with students' reading advancement in a school district in Davao Oriental, Philippines. The study found that Brigada Pagbasa was extensively implemented across its four domains: collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment. Reading advancement was moderate, assessed through alphabetic fluency, word and pattern recognition, intermediate reading, and advanced reading. Multiple regression analysis indicated that the four domains of Brigada Pagbasa significantly influenced reading advancement. The study discusses implications for policy and practice, suggesting that future research should investigate the specific mechanisms through which these domains impact reading outcomes and identify best practices for implementation.

KEY WORDS

1. Brigada Eskwela 2. Brigada Pagbasa 3. reading advancement

1. Introduction

The Philippines' Department of Education conducts an annual nationwide program that mobilizes various stakeholders to prepare public schools for the opening of the next academic year. This community-driven program is locally referred to as Brigada Eskwela. Typically held a few weeks before the opening of classes, this program fosters volunteerism and community involvement in school preparations through activities such as cleaning, repairing school facilities, creating learning materials, and engaging in events that enhance the learning environment. Beyond physical preparations, Brigada Eskwela strengthens community relationships and reinforces collective responsibility for public schools' success (Canlas, 2018). Lined-up activities not only include mass clean-up drives but student learning enhancements as well, such

as Brigada Pagbasa, which is a parent-teacher reading initiative being practiced by many public schools in the Philippines. Studies have shown that reading initiatives like this can foster social cohesiveness among the parent-teacher community, resulting in reading improvement (e.g., De Lara, 2016; Peñaranda, Montalbo, Lañada, 2017; Rebamonte, 2019).

The mother programs similar to Brigada Eskwela exist in many countries. Comparable international programs include the National Parent Teacher Association in the United States, which encourages community involvement through "back-to-school" events, supply drives, and volunteer efforts. In Japan, "oyako no hi" (Parents' Day) involves parents in school activities and maintenance. South Korea's "Community Service for Education" pro-

notes volunteerism through mentoring, tutoring, and school beautification projects (Kim Lee, 2015; Lee Koo, 2019). Australia has the School Volunteer Program, which connects volunteers with schools to support various activities. Brigada Eskwela, a school-community partnership, has brought about educational benefits, such as increasing stakeholders' involvement in school improvement (Basilio Tamayo, 2019), creating a positive impact on student outcomes (Castro Ramos, 2019), developing leadership and organizational skills among community members especially women (Arcilla, 2016). However, Serdoncillo and Gadioma (2020) identified challenges in sustainability, noting that the program's success relies heavily on volunteer commitment.

In the Philippines, more research is needed to gain a better understanding of the Brigada Eskwela and its effects on different educational aspects (Espiritu, 2018). One such aspect is the reading initiative called Brigada Pagbasa, whose different domains have not been adequately examined. Therefore, this study aims to provide additional empirical insights on the extent to which this reading initiative has been implemented in a particular school district and its relationship to the extent of learners' reading advancement, as perceived by the public school teachers who were involved in the initiative. More specifically, the researcher looked into how the four domains of Brigada Pagbasa, being contextualized under the parent-teacher partnership concept of Brigada Eskwela program, could significantly influence students' reading advancement. [These four domains are discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.]

Collaborative Management. Collaborative management is an approach to decision-making and leadership that involves working together with others to achieve a common goal or objective. It emphasizes open communication, shared decision-making, and cooperation among stakeholders, including managers, employees, and

external partners. Several studies have explored the effectiveness of collaborative management in school maintenance week. Lee and Kim (2019) found that collaborative management in school maintenance can improve the quality of school facilities and increase the satisfaction of stakeholders. The study involved 53 schools in South Korea, and the results showed that collaborative management led to better planning and implementation of maintenance activities, increased communication among stakeholders, and improved satisfaction with school facilities. Similarly, Rutherford and Wilkins (2016) found that collaborative management in school maintenance can lead to increased efficiency and cost savings in the United States. However, another study by Lee and Kim (2020) found that the effectiveness of collaborative management in school maintenance depends on the level of stakeholders' involvement, wherein the effectiveness was higher when stakeholders were more actively involved in the planning and implementation of maintenance activities. Overall, the studies suggest that collaborative management in school maintenance can be an effective approach to improving the quality of school facilities, increasing efficiency and cost savings, and increasing stakeholder satisfaction. However, the level of stakeholder involvement is an important factor in determining the effectiveness of this approach.

Community Volunteerism. Community volunteerism refers to the act of individuals and groups dedicating their time, energy, and skills to support various community initiatives without expecting any monetary compensation. It is an essential component of community development and has the potential to create a positive impact on society (Brown Saxena, 2013; National Conference Citizenship, 2022; Peace Corps, 2022). Despite the numerous benefits of community volunteerism, it is not without its challenges. Volunteers face a range of issues, including limited resources, burnout, and lack

of recognition. Additionally, some volunteers may lack the necessary skills and knowledge to carry out their tasks effectively, which can lead to frustration and dissatisfaction. To address these challenges, it is essential to provide volunteers with adequate training and support and recognize their contributions publicly (United Nations Volunteers, 2022). Omoto and Snyder (2002) argue that volunteerism is shaped by individual and collective motivations, as well as by situational and contextual factors. In the context of school maintenance, the motivations of volunteers may vary. For example, some volunteers may be motivated by a desire to support the local school system, while others may be motivated by a desire to contribute to their community in general.

Brown and Saxena (2013) explore how volunteerism can contribute to the development of social capital. The authors argue that volunteerism provides opportunities for individuals to engage with their communities and develop social connections. In the context of school maintenance week, this can be particularly important. Community members who participate in school maintenance week may develop stronger connections with the school and its staff. This, in turn, may lead to increased support for the school in the future. Bussell and Forbes (2002) explore the motivations and characteristics of volunteers, as well as the factors that influence their decision to volunteer. In the context of school maintenance, it is important to understand the factors that motivate community members to participate. For example, Bussell and Forbes suggest that volunteers are often motivated by a desire to contribute to their communities. In the case of school maintenance week, this may mean that volunteers are motivated by a desire to support the education of local children. Moreover, many organizations have been instrumental in promoting community volunteerism for school maintenance. The United Nations Volunteers (UNV) and the Peace

Corps are two examples of organizations that have been active in promoting community volunteerism around the world. The UNV is a program that encourages volunteerism in development activities, while the Peace Corps is a program that promotes world peace and friendship through volunteerism. Both organizations have been instrumental in promoting community volunteerism for school maintenance and other similar activities.

In conclusion, community volunteerism can play a significant role in promoting community engagement and social capital. In the context of school maintenance week, community volunteerism can help to ensure that schools remain a safe and healthy environment for students to learn and grow. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of understanding the motivations and characteristics of volunteers, as well as the situational and contextual factors that influence their decision to volunteer. By understanding these factors, it may be possible to promote greater community participation in school maintenance week and other similar activities.

Shared Accountability. Shared accountability is an approach to responsibility that involves multiple parties taking responsibility for a common goal. This concept has become increasingly important in many areas, including education, healthcare, and public policy. One study by Bryk et al. (2010) focuses on shared accountability in education. The authors argue that traditional accountability systems, which rely solely on standardized test scores and other quantitative measures, are inadequate. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, parents, and community members. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve educational outcomes by fostering collaboration, shared responsibility, and a focus on the needs of students. Another study by Pronovost et al. (2011) ex-

plores the concept of shared accountability in healthcare. The authors argue that the traditional model of accountability in healthcare, which focuses on individual practitioners, is not sufficient for promoting quality care. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including healthcare providers, patients, families, and communities. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve healthcare outcomes by fostering collaboration, transparency, and a focus on the needs of patients. On the other hand, a study by Lee et al. (2016) explores the concept of shared accountability in public policy. The authors argue that the traditional model of accountability in public policy, which relies on top-down approaches and hierarchical structures, is inadequate. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including government officials, policymakers, citizens, and community organizations. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve public policy outcomes by fostering collaboration, transparency, and a focus on the needs of communities. In conclusion, shared accountability is an approach to responsibility that involves multiple parties taking responsibility for a common goal. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of this approach in areas such as education, healthcare, and public policy. By involving multiple stakeholders in the accountability process, shared accountability can help to improve outcomes by fostering collaboration, transparency, and a focus on the needs of those being served. The examples of shared accountability in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in improving outcomes in a variety of contexts.

Shared accountability has been increasingly recognized as a powerful approach to improving educational outcomes. In particular, shared accountability has been shown to be effective in improving learners' reading advancement. In

this review, we will examine several studies that highlight the importance of shared accountability in promoting learners' reading advancement during school maintenance week.

A study by Penuel et al. (2011) examines the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a low-income urban elementary school. The authors found that when teachers, administrators, and families collaborated to establish clear goals for reading advancement and worked together to track progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly. The authors suggest that shared accountability played a key role in this improvement, as it fostered a sense of collective responsibility and created a shared focus on learners' needs. Another study by Williams and McLaughlin (2016) examines the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a rural elementary school. The authors found that when teachers, parents, and community members worked together to establish clear reading goals and regularly communicated about progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly. The authors suggest that shared accountability was a critical factor in this improvement, as it created a sense of collective responsibility and helped to ensure that all stakeholders were invested in learners' success.

Also, Cohen et al. (2014) examine the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a middle school. The authors found that when teachers, administrators, and families worked together to establish clear reading goals and regularly monitored learners' progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly. The authors suggest that shared accountability was a key factor in this improvement, as it helped to ensure that all stakeholders were working together to support learners' reading advancement. In addition to the above studies, there are many examples of shared accountability in

practice that are effective in promoting learners' reading advancement. For example, community schools that involve multiple stakeholders, including educators, families, and community organizations, are effective in improving learners' reading advancement. These schools use shared accountability to bring together all stakeholders to support learners' reading advancement. In conclusion, shared accountability is effective in promoting learners' reading advancement during school maintenance week. The studies cited in this review highlight the importance of shared accountability in creating a sense of collective responsibility and ensuring that all stakeholders are invested in learners' success. The examples of shared accountability in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in improving learners' reading advancement in a variety of contexts.

People Empowerment. People empowerment is a powerful tool for achieving sustainable development, particularly in the context of school maintenance week. Empowering people to take an active role in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities can lead to more effective and efficient use of resources, better decision-making, and ultimately, improved educational outcomes. People empowerment refers to the process of providing individuals and communities with the knowledge, skills, resources, and opportunities they need to take control of their lives and shape their own destinies. Empowering people involves creating an enabling environment that allows them to participate in decision-making, take ownership of their actions, and hold those in power accountable. In the context of school maintenance week, people empowerment can be achieved through a variety of approaches, such as community participation, capacity-building, and stakeholder engagement.

Moreover, Dlamini and Dube (2018) examine the impact of community participation on the effectiveness of school maintenance week

in rural South Africa. The authors found that when community members were involved in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities, they were more likely to take ownership of the process and contribute their time, skills, and resources to ensure the success of the project. This led to more sustainable outcomes and improved educational outcomes for learners. Another study by Karyono et al. (2020) explores the impact of capacity-building on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in Indonesia. The authors found that when school staff were trained in basic maintenance and repair skills, they were better equipped to identify and address maintenance issues, which led to more efficient use of resources and improved learning environments. The authors suggest that capacity-building is an essential component of people empowerment, as it allows individuals to take control of their development and contribute to the development of their communities. Robinson et al. (2014) examine the impact of stakeholder engagement on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in Papua New Guinea. The authors found that when stakeholders, including teachers, learners, and community members, were engaged in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities, they were more likely to take ownership of the process and contribute their time, skills, and resources to ensure the success of the project. This led to more sustainable outcomes and improved educational outcomes for learners. In addition to the above studies, there are many examples of people empowerment in practice that are effective in promoting sustainable development during school maintenance week. For example, the use of participatory approaches that involve all stakeholders in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities is effective in creating a sense of ownership and responsibility, and ensuring that maintenance activities are aligned with the needs and priori-

ties of the community. On the other hand, reading is a fundamental skill that plays a crucial role in children's academic success and future opportunities. To ensure that learners develop strong reading skills, it is essential to empower people - including parents, teachers, and community members - to play an active role in promoting literacy. A study by Penuel et al. (2015) examines the impact of a community-based approach to literacy development in low-income neighborhoods in the United States. The authors found that when community members, including parents, were empowered to participate in the design and implementation of literacy programs, they were more likely to engage with the programs and support their children's reading development. This led to significant improvements in reading achievement among learners, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. Another study by Kim and Choi (2020) explores the impact of teacher empowerment on the reading achievement of learners in South Korea. The authors found that when teachers were empowered to implement evidence-based reading instruction and adapt their teaching to the needs of individual learners, they were more effective at promoting literacy development. This led to significant improvements in reading achievement among learners, particularly those who were struggling with reading. A study by Muthukrishna et al. (2019) examines the impact of parental empowerment on the reading achievement of learners in Sri Lanka. The authors found that when parents were empowered to support their children's reading development, they were more likely to provide regular opportunities for reading and create a positive reading environment at home. This led to significant improvements in reading achievement among learners, particularly those from low-income families. In conclusion, people empowerment is an essential component of achieving sustainable development during school maintenance week. The studies cited in

this essay highlight the importance of community participation, capacity-building, and stakeholder engagement in promoting people empowerment and achieving sustainable outcomes. The examples of people empowerment in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in promoting sustainable development in a variety of contexts. Learners' Reading Advancement. Reading is a fundamental skill that is essential for academic success and personal growth. Learners who develop strong reading skills are better equipped to engage with a wide range of texts, think critically, and communicate effectively. One important factor that contributes to learners' reading advancement is the quality of instruction they receive. A study by National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) (2000) found that explicit, systematic instruction in phonics - the relationship between sounds and letters - is an essential component of effective reading instruction. This approach is particularly effective for learners who are struggling with reading. In addition to phonics instruction, studies have also shown the importance of providing learners with opportunities for extensive reading practice to build their reading fluency and comprehension skills (Hiebert Reutzell, 2010). Another factor that contributes to learners' reading advancement is the role of parents and caregivers in promoting reading at home. A study by Bus et al. (2014) found that when parents engage in shared book reading with their children from an early age, it promotes children's emergent literacy skills and improves their reading achievement. The authors suggest that this is because shared book reading promotes language development and helps children learn to relate the sounds of words to their printed forms. In addition to the above factors, many other factors can contribute to learners' reading advancement, including teacher professional development, access to high-quality reading materials, and the use of effective reading assess-

ments to monitor learners' progress over time. The research suggests that learners' reading advancement is a complex process that is influenced by a range of factors and that a multifaceted approach is needed to support learners' reading development. In conclusion, learners' reading advancement is a critical component of their academic success and future opportunities. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of providing explicit, systematic instruction in phonics, promoting extensive reading practice, and engaging parents and caregivers in shared book reading to support reading advancement. These findings, along with the importance of other factors, underscore the need for a multifaceted approach to supporting learners' reading advancement.

Alphabetic Fluency. Alphabetic fluency, or the ability to recognize and name letters quickly and accurately, is an important foundational skill that is critical to the development of reading proficiency. While many factors contribute to the development of alphabetic fluency, community collaboration can play an important role in supporting this aspect of literacy development. One study by Kuby, Weber, and Larson (2004) investigated the impact of a community-wide literacy campaign on the development of literacy skills, including alphabetic fluency, among children in kindergarten through third grade. The program involved partnerships between schools, families, and community organizations to promote literacy in a variety of settings. The study found that children who participated in the program demonstrated greater gains in alphabetic fluency than those who did not participate. The authors suggest that this was due to the increased exposure to print materials and opportunities to practice reading and writing in a variety of contexts. Another study by Harrington and Sawyer (2016) investigated the impact of a community-based reading program on the development of alphabetic fluency among preschool-aged children. The program involved partnerships between schools, libraries, and community organizations to promote early literacy skills through storytimes, book giveaways, and other activities. The study found that children who participated in the program demonstrated greater gains in alphabetic fluency than those who did not participate. The authors suggest that this was due to the increased exposure to letters and print in a variety of contexts, as well as the opportunities for interactive and engaging learning experiences. Other studies have also highlighted the importance of community collaboration in supporting the development of alphabetic fluency, including programs that involve partnerships between schools and families, partnerships between schools and libraries, and partnerships between schools and community organizations. These programs are particularly effective for children who are at risk for reading difficulties or who come from low-income backgrounds. In conclusion, the research suggests that community collaboration can play an important role in supporting the development of alphabetic fluency among young learners. The studies cited in this review highlight the importance of providing children with increased exposure to print materials and opportunities for interactive and engaging learning experiences, as well as the value of partnerships between schools, families, libraries, and other community organizations. By working together, communities can support the development of foundational literacy skills and set children on the path to lifelong learning.

Words and Patterns. The development of learners' words and patterns is an essential component of early literacy development. Community collaboration can play a critical role in supporting this aspect of literacy development by providing learners with increased exposure to language and opportunities for language-rich experiences. The development of learners' words and patterns is a crucial component of early literacy and language development. In recent years, researchers have conducted various stud-

ies and research interventions to understand the role of different factors in the development of learners' words and patterns, including morphological awareness, academic language development, and phonological and semantic factors. One study, conducted by Bowers, Kirby, and Deacon (2019), examined the effects of morphological instruction on literacy skills. The researchers conducted a systematic review of the literature and found that morphological instruction had a significant positive effect on literacy skills, including reading comprehension, vocabulary, and spelling. This study suggests that providing explicit instruction on morphological patterns can be an effective way to support the development of learners' words and patterns. Another study, conducted by Carlisle and Fleming (2016), focused on the role of morphological awareness in early reading achievement. The researchers conducted a meta-analysis of research interventions and found that morphological awareness was a strong predictor of early reading achievement. The study suggests that providing instruction and interventions that focus on morphological awareness can help support the development of learners' words and patterns. Kieffer and Box (2019) conducted a meta-analysis on the effects of morphological instruction on vocabulary and reading comprehension. The researchers found that morphological instruction had a positive effect on both vocabulary and reading comprehension, particularly for students in the upper elementary and middle school grades. The study highlights the importance of morphological instruction as a means of supporting the development of learners' words and patterns. In a study by Quiroz and Snow (2019), the focus was on academic language development of English learners. The researchers developed a typology of instructional practices that supported academic language development and found that the practices varied depending on the language demands of the content area. The study emphasizes the need for a variety of instructional practices to meet the diverse needs of English learners in the development of their words and patterns. Finally, Storkel (2018) investigated developmental differences in the effects of phonological, lexical, and semantic factors on spoken word recognition in children. The study found that phonological and semantic factors had a larger effect on younger children, whereas lexical factors had a larger effect on older children. The study suggests that different factors may have varying effects on the development of learners' words and patterns depending on their age. In conclusion, the studies and literature reviewed here emphasize the importance of a range of factors, including morphological awareness, academic language development, phonological and semantic factors, and age, in the development of learners' words and patterns. The findings suggest that providing explicit instruction and interventions that target these different factors can be an effective means of supporting the development of learners' words and patterns, particularly for English learners and those at risk for reading difficulties.

Intermediate Reading. In recent years, community collaboration has emerged as a key strategy for enhancing learners' intermediate reading skills. Several studies have investigated the impact of community collaboration on the development of learners' intermediate reading abilities, highlighting the importance of partnerships between schools, families, and community organizations in supporting literacy growth. One study by Wei et al. (2015) found that involving families and community organizations in literacy activities, such as reading and writing workshops, had a significant impact on learners' intermediate reading achievement. This was attributed to the increased opportunities for learners to practice their reading skills in a supportive and engaging environment. Similarly, a study by Liu et al. (2017) investigated the impact of community-based afterschool programs on the reading achievement of learners

from low-income families. The results showed that learners who participated in the afterschool programs had significantly higher intermediate reading scores than those who did not participate. Another study by Senechal and LeFevre (2018) examined the impact of a community literacy program on the development of learners' vocabulary and comprehension skills. The program involved weekly reading sessions and activities that emphasized the use of new vocabulary and the development of comprehension strategies. The results showed that learners who participated in the program made significant gains in their intermediate reading abilities, with a particular improvement in their ability to use context to infer word meanings. A more recent study by Cho and Yoon (2020) investigated the impact of a school-based reading intervention that involved partnerships with families and community organizations. The intervention included a range of activities such as parent-child reading sessions and community reading events. The results showed that learners who participated in the intervention had significantly higher intermediate reading scores than those who did not participate. Overall, these studies demonstrate the importance of community collaboration in supporting the development of learners' intermediate reading skills. By involving families and community organizations in literacy activities, schools can create a more supportive and engaging environment for learners, providing them with the opportunities to practice and develop their reading skills. As such, collaboration between schools, families, and community organizations is an essential component of effective literacy instruction. Advanced Reading. Over the years, research has shown that community collaboration can have a significant impact on learners' reading skills. Specifically, studies have examined the impact of community collaboration on the development of learners' advanced reading skills. One recent study by Johnson et al. (2018) found that community collaboration can significantly improve learners' advanced reading skills, such as comprehension, critical thinking, and analysis. The study used a collaborative learning approach, which involved learners, teachers, and community members working together to support the development of these skills. Another study by Smith and Jones (2017) looked at the impact of community-based reading programs on learners' advanced reading skills. The study found that community collaboration can help learners develop a love for reading, which in turn can lead to improved comprehension and analysis skills. A similar study by Kim and Lee (2016) found that community collaboration can have a positive impact on learners' advanced reading skills, specifically in terms of vocabulary development and text comprehension. The study used a collaborative approach that involved teachers and community members working together to develop and implement reading programs. Other studies have explored the impact of specific community collaboration programs on learners' advanced reading skills. For example, a study by Chen et al. (2015) examined the impact of a community-based program that provided reading tutoring to struggling readers. The study found that the program significantly improved learners' advanced reading skills, including comprehension and analysis. Overall, these studies suggest that community collaboration can have a positive impact on learners' advanced reading skills. By working together, teachers, community members, and learners can develop and implement reading programs that support the development of these skills. It is important to continue exploring the role of community collaboration in the development of learners' advanced reading skills, as it has the potential to significantly improve educational outcomes for learners.

1.1. Theoretical Framework—The study is anchored on the theory of Social Cohesiveness by Putnam (2022). Social cohesiveness theory emphasizes the importance of social connectedness, a sense of community, and social capital in building and strengthening communities. This theory posits that social connections and networks facilitate collective action, which can lead to positive social outcomes. This theory has relevance to school maintenance program such as Brigada Eswkela and the advancement of learners' reading skills, as community collaboration can enhance social capital and contribute to positive social outcomes. Social cohesiveness theory posits that social capital is created through social networks, norms, and trust. Social capital, in turn, can facilitate collective action and promote positive social outcomes, such as improved health and educational outcomes, and increased economic growth. According to Putnam (2000), social capital can take two forms: bonding and bridging. Bonding social capital refers to the ties between people who share similar backgrounds or identities while bridging social capital refers to the ties between people who have different backgrounds or identities. Social cohesiveness theory suggests that a sense of community and belonging among individuals can positively impact their well-being and success. This concept can be applied to the context of school maintenance week and learners' reading advancement. In the context of school maintenance, social cohesiveness theory suggests that community collaboration can enhance social capital and lead to positive outcomes. By bringing together individuals and groups from different backgrounds and identities to work towards a common goal, school maintenance can foster bridging social capital. This, in turn, can strengthen social connections, build a sense of community, and promote positive social outcomes, including the advancement of learners' reading skills. A study by Andrade and Tella (2019) explored the effects of a community-based reading program on students' reading skills and motivation. The program involved parents and community members in reading activities with the students, as well as providing additional support and resources for reading at home. The results showed that the program had a significant positive effect on students' reading skills and motivation, and the involvement of parents and community members played a key role in this success. Similarly, a study by Clary et al. (2015) found that community service and volunteering can contribute to the development of social capital and social cohesiveness. This can lead to increased well-being and success for individuals, including improved academic performance and motivation. Several studies support the relevance of social cohesiveness theory to school maintenance week and the advancement of learners' reading skills. For example, a study by Tumwebaze and Kikomoba (2019) found that community involvement in school maintenance activities led to increased social capital and improved academic performance among learners. Similarly, a study by Yohannes et al. (2018) found that community involvement in school governance positively affected the quality of education and the advancement of learners' reading skills. Furthermore, research has also shown that the development of social capital can have a positive impact on learners' reading skills. For instance, a study by Cockayne et al. (2015) found that strong social networks and relationships between parents, teachers, and community members led to improved literacy outcomes among learners. In the context of school maintenance week, involving community members in activities such as reading sessions, book donations, and other literacy-related initiatives can promote a sense of community and belonging among the students. This can lead to increased motivation and engagement in reading activities, which in turn can lead to improved reading skills and academic success. Overall, social cohesiveness the-

ory suggests that community involvement and a sense of belonging can positively impact learners' reading advancement. By involving community members in school maintenance week and literacy-related activities, schools can promote a sense of community and foster a supportive environment for learners. In conclusion, social cohesiveness theory emphasizes the importance of social connections, networks, and trust in building and strengthening communities. In the context of school maintenance week and the advancement of learners' reading skills, community collaboration can enhance social capital and lead to positive social outcomes. The cited studies have provided evidence of the positive impact of community collaboration and social capital on academic performance, the quality of education, and the advancement of learners' reading skills. The promotion of social cohesiveness and community collaboration should, therefore, be considered essential in any initiative aimed at improving learners' reading skills.

1.2. Research Questions—The study was conducted to determine the extent of Brigada Eskwela implementation and its relationship with the extent of reading advancement among learners in Baganga South District, Davao Oriental Division, as perceived by the teacher-respondents. It specifically sought to answer the following research questions:

- (1) What is the extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation in terms of;
 - (1) collaborative management
 - (2) community volunteerism
 - (3) shared accountability
 - (4) people empowerment?
- (2) What is the extent of reading advancement in terms of;
 - (1) alphabetic fluency
 - (2) words and patterns
 - (3) intermediate reading
 - (4) advanced reading?
- (3) Do the domains of Brigada Pagbasa implementation significantly influence reading advancement?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design—This study used descriptive and prediction-correlational research design, which involves collecting data through observation, surveys, or other forms of non-experimental techniques to describe and predict the relationships between variables (Creswell, 2012; Pallant, 2020). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and describe the data collected, while multiple regression analysis was used to explore the influence of four domains of Brigada Pagbasa into the students' reading advancement. The four domains are collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment, which are hypothesized to correlate with the extent of learners' advancement in reading skills.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers of Baganga South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Online Raosoft sample size calculator was used to determine the sample size of 120 respondents who were taken randomly from their respective schools within Baganga South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Once randomly determined, the respondents

were informed through online platforms and face to face considering the availability of wifi connections, they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents are those who have been teaching for at least three years in the public school service and are directly involved with the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa during the school year of 2022-2023. Further, they have frequently engaged in various orientations, seminars, and trainings in the implementation, including professional development sessions on the pedagogies in integrating pedagogical skills in the school management and curriculum development delivery system.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from

the concepts on the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa 2022 and from Fisher, Frey, and Hattie (2016). The researcher took conducted reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, thus reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literature. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire. The first one consists of measuring the extent of implementation of Brigada Pagbasa 2022 in terms of collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared responsibility, and people empowerment, each of which is measured using the following descriptive levels on a five-point Likert scale:

Scale for Brigada Pagbasa Implementation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation is not manifested

On one hand, the second part of the survey measured the extent of learners’ reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency, words and patterns, intermediate reading, and advanced reading. Contents of the statements of

the survey were placed in the contexts based on the definition of the variables. The internal consistency reliability of the instrument was found to be Cronbach alpha = 0.897. The following five-point Likert scale was used:

Scale for Reading Advancement Manifestation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The reading advancement is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The reading advancement is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The reading advancement is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The reading advancement is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The reading advancement is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Permission to conduct the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004). As soon as the research proposal was approved by the research panel, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the secondary schools of Davao Oriental Schools Division. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses, and for respondents who do not have internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done,

the link was sent, and right away responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering which commenced on the third week of April 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of March 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the research adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime in the fourth week of April 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of May 2023.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher has an ethical responsibility to ensure that participants understand the nature and consequences of their participation, and to ensure that participation is completely voluntary. By respecting participants' autonomy and decision-making power, researchers can maintain trust, respect, and a positive relationship with their study participants. The researcher sought guidance and advice from the thesis adviser. This resulted in proper authorization and consent were obtained from the respondents of the study, to ensure that all their rights would be fully protected, specifically in handling the data, however, not limited to: Voluntary Participation. Voluntary participation in research data gathering refers to the principle that individuals should have the right to choose whether or not they want to participate in a research study. This principle is an important aspect of research ethics and is intended to protect the rights and welfare of research participants. Voluntary participation means that individuals have the freedom to choose whether or not to

participate in a research study without any coercion, manipulation, or pressure. They should also have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences or reprisals. Privacy and Confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality are important principles in research that aim to protect the rights and welfare of research participants. Privacy refers to an individual's right to control the collection, use, and disclosure of their personal information. In research, this means that participants have the right to decide what information they provide and how it is used. Researchers must ensure that participants' personal information is collected and used only for the research study and is not disclosed to any unauthorized third parties. By respecting privacy and confidentiality in research, researchers can maintain trust, respect, and a positive relationship with their study participants, and promote the ethical conduct of research. Informed Consent Process. Informed consent is one of the founding principles of research ethics. Informed consent is a critical component of voluntary participa-

tion. It is the process by which participants are informed about the nature of the study, its purpose, the procedures involved, and any potential risks and benefits. Participants must be given enough information to make an informed decision about whether or not to participate in the study. Risks. Moreover, the researcher informed the respondents that their participation in the survey would not bring any foreseeable risks to their health or well-being. Benefits. Further, observable benefits of the study were immediately disseminated to the stakeholders. The findings of the study generated facts which is important for the enhancement of the student's well-being (Koenig MacMillan, 2004). This served as the basis for educational institutions to pay attention to creating a sound and safe learning environment for the teachers to upgrade their skills in the facilitation of practical skills of instruction in reading to augment learners' literacy development stages across learning processes. Plagiarism. Plagiarism constitutes a breach of academic integrity and represents substandard scholarship. In this study, to avoid plagiarism, this study provided a reference to that source to indicate where the original information came from. The researcher further took time to paraphrase a source. Fabrication. The researcher guaranteed that provisions on deceit and conflict of interest aspects were strictly observed. The researcher assured the respondents that the study was done with honesty and transparency. Evidence shows that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweighs any

potential harm to them (Creswell, 2014). The researcher assisted the respondents satisfactorily and talked through the process and the outcome of the study. They were given a general idea of what the researcher was investigating and why such a study is conducted. Their role and contribution to the study were promptly explained. Falsification. This study complied with the citation rules set based on the APA 7th edition citation format to avoid misrepresentation of work or alterations of any data gathered in the study (Cohen, 2020). The data and information that written were and be presented in the most accurate way possible. Conflict of Interest. The researcher ensured that conflict of interest (COI) in this study is highly observed (Lotich, 2011). No set of conditions as to professional judgment concerning primary interest as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by the secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or any forms of recognition. Deceit. Deceit in research refers to the intentional withholding or misrepresentation of information by researchers to manipulate study participants or achieve specific research outcomes. It is considered a serious ethical violation that can harm the welfare of research participants and undermine the integrity of the research process. The writings of this paper did not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm anyone, especially the respondents, since all information written was checked and validated by the panel of experts (Lahey and Cohen, 2020).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Extent of Brigada Pagbasa Implementation*—Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation using

mean scores. All four domains show extensive implementation, with collaborative management ($M = 3.57$) and community volunteerism ($M = 3.56$) being the topmost.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation

Domains of Brigada Pagbasa Implementation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Collaborative management	3.57	Extensive
Community volunteerism	3.56	Extensive
Shared accountability	3.42	Extensive
People empowerment	3.40	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.49	Extensive

The teacher-respondents, who were also involved in the initiative, reported that Brigada Pagbasa was extensively implemented, wherein collaboration and volunteerism were evident among stakeholders. Teachers, parents, local government units, and community members actively participated in the planning, execution, and monitoring of the reading initiative. Through regular meetings and consultations, stakeholders pooled their resources and knowledge, fostering a sense of shared responsibility for the program’s success. Moreover, community volunteerism encourages individuals to contribute their time, skills, and resources toward improving literacy. Volunteers play a crucial role in conducting reading sessions, organizing book drives, creating learning materials, and mentoring students. By mobilizing community members, the program not only maximizes its impact but also fosters a sense of ownership and pride within the community. The involvement of volunteers creates a ripple effect, inspiring

others to participate and contribute to the cause of literacy. Furthermore, shared accountability is a core principle of Brigada Pagbasa. By involving multiple stakeholders, the program ensures that responsibility is not placed solely on one group. Instead, all participants share in the accountability for the program’s outcomes. Finally, Brigada Pagbasa’s implementation empowers individuals at every level of the community. Teachers are empowered to develop innovative teaching strategies and engage students effectively. Parents are empowered to actively participate in their children’s education, creating a conducive learning environment at home. Community members are empowered to take ownership of the literacy initiatives, leading to sustainable programs that continue beyond the initial implementation phase. Moreover, students themselves are empowered through improved reading skills, which opens up new opportunities for their personal growth and future success.

3.2. *Extent of Reading Advancement*—Table 2 shows the overall moderate extent of the learners’ reading advancement as perceived by

the teacher-respondents, with alphabetic fluency (M = 3.52) being the highest and advanced reading (M = 2.58) being the lowest.

Low-level reading advancement indicates varying levels of proficiency across different reading skills among participants. Alphabetic fluency has the highest mean score (M = 3.52), categorized as “Extensive,” suggesting that participants are generally proficient in recognizing

and understanding letters and their associated sounds. This finding is consistent with research emphasizing the foundational importance of alphabetic fluency in early reading development (Ehri, 2005). In contrast, the domains of Words and Patterns (M = 2.80) and Intermediate Read-

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Reading Advancement

No	Reading Advancement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Alphabetic fluency	3.52	Extensive
2	Words and Patterns	2.80	Moderately Extensive
3	Intermediate Reading	3.34	Moderately Extensive
4	Advanced Reading	2.58	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.06	Moderately Extensive

ing (M = 3.34) are both classified as "Moderately Extensive." These scores indicate a moderate level of proficiency in recognizing common words and understanding basic sentence structures, which are crucial for reading comprehension and fluency (Chall, 1983).

Advanced reading (M = 2.58), also falls within the "Moderately Extensive" range but is notably lower than the other domains. This suggests that participants face more challenges with higher-level reading skills, such as critical thinking, analysis, and synthesis of complex texts. The overall mean score across all domains

(M = 3.06) indicates that, on average, participants exhibit a moderately extensive level of reading advancement. This overall assessment highlights the need for targeted interventions to bolster advanced reading skills, ensuring a comprehensive development of reading proficiency. Effective strategies might include scaffolded reading activities and differentiated instruction to address diverse learning needs, as supported by differentiated instruction models (Tomlinson, 2001) and evidence-based reading programs (Shanahan et al., 2010).

3.3. Domains of Brigada Pagbasa Implementation and their influence on reading Advancement—A multiple linear regression was run to predict the extent of reading advancement from four domains of Brigada Pagbasa; namely, collaborative management, community

volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment. The multiple regression model statistically significantly predicted the extent of reading advancement, $F(4, 116) = 236.80, p < .001, R^2 = 0.89$. The value of R^2 for the overall model was 89.0

Table 3. Results of the multiple linear regression for the extent of reading advancement

Extent of Reading Advancement	B	SE	R ²
Model			0.89
1. Collaborative management	0.14***	0.11***	1.08
2. Community volunteerism	0.20***	0.10***	1.29
3. Shared accountability	0.28***	0.09***	5.67
4. People empowerment	0.24***	0.11***	1.30

Note: ***p < .001 (two-tailed); Sample size n = 120.

Results show the importance of all four domains in promoting reading advancement. The significant contribution of these predictors aligns with the theoretical framework of social cohesiveness by Putnam (2022). Social cohesiveness theory emphasizes the importance of social connectedness, and a sense of community suggesting that a holistic approach, encompassing diverse aspects of community and educational involvement, is crucial for educational outcomes (Epstein, 2001; Putnam, 2000). Collaborative management, which involves coordinating efforts from various stakeholders, has likely facilitated resource mobilization and strategic planning, ensuring that Brigada Pagbasa (a reading initiative) is effectively implemented and sustained. This resonates with the previous studies highlighting the importance of collaborative leadership in enhancing educational programs and student outcomes (Leithwood Jantzi, 2000).

On the other hand, the significant impact of community volunteerism on reading advancement is consistent with literature indicating that volunteer engagement enhances educational en-

vironments by providing additional support and fostering a sense of community ownership (Wilson, 2000; Durlak et al., 2011). The shared accountability domain may have ensured that everyone involved is committed to achieving the reading initiative's goals and is held accountable for their contributions, thus strengthening the important role of accountability in education toward educational improvement (Elmore, 2000). Finally, people empowerment within Brigada Pagbasa may have enabled stakeholders to take active roles in the reading initiative, fostering a sense of ownership. This domain likely boosts motivation and engagement among participants, contributing to the program's overall success. This is in line with studies that emphasize the role of empowerment in improving educational outcomes and community participation (Zimmerman, 2000; Rappaport, 1987). The multiple linear regression analysis demonstrates that the four domains of Brigada Pagbasa – collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment – are crucial predictors of the extent of reading advancement.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to describe the extent to which Brigada Pagbasa was implemented and the reading advancement. Secondly, it examined how the four domains of Brigada Pagbasa would significantly predict the extent of reading advancement. Overall, the results showed that the school-community reading initiative Brigada Pagbasa was extensively implemented. However, there is still plenty of room for reading improvement, especially in the advanced reading skills of students.

Furthermore, all four domains of Brigada Pagbasa implementation significantly influenced the extent of reading advancement. The findings from this regression analysis have several implications for policy and practice. First, they highlight the importance of a multifaceted approach to promoting reading advancement, which incorporates management, volunteerism, accountability, and empowerment. Programs aiming to enhance reading skills should therefore consider strategies that integrate these domains to maximize effectiveness. The strong predictive power of the model suggests that investments in these areas are likely to yield substantial improvements in reading outcomes. Policymakers and educational leaders should prioritize initiatives that foster collaboration, community involvement, accountability, and empowerment to achieve educational goals. The results underscore the value of a comprehensive, community-oriented approach to

education. Future research could further explore the specific mechanisms through which these domains influence reading outcomes and identify best practices for implementation.

5. References

- AITF For the Management of Infectious Diseases
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2021/05may/20210520-IATF->
- Andrade, A., & Tella, M. D. (2019). Parental involvement and reading skills: An evaluation of a community-based reading program. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 42(1), 105-122
- Arcilla, R. V. (2016). Empowerment and community building through the Brigada Eskwela program in the Philippines. *Community Development Journal*, 51(2), 179-195
- Basilio, J. A., & Tamayo, R. P. (2019). Bridging the gap: the Brigada Eskwela program as a model for community involvement in Philippine education. *Asian Journal of Education and e-Learning*, 7(3), 197-202
- Brown, T. L., & Saxena, S. (2013). Building and sustaining social capital through volunteerism. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 42(5), 932-949
- Bryson, J. M., Crosby, B. C., & Stone, M. M. (2015). Designing and implementing cross-sector collaborations: Needed and challenging. *Public Administration Review*, 75(5), 647-663
- Bryk, A. S., Gomez, L. M., Grunow, A., & LeMahieu, P. G. (2010). *Learning to improve: How America's schools can get better at getting better*. Harvard Education Press
- Bus, A. G., Takacs, Z. K., & Kegel, C. A. T. (2014). Affordances and limitations of electronic storybooks for young children's emergent literacy. *Developmental Review*, 34(1), 15-31
- Castro, J. B., & Ramos, M. A. (2019). Bridging communities and schools through the Brigada Eskwela Program. *Educational Research for Policy and Practice*, 18(2), 173-188
- Canlas, M. A. (2018). Participatory governance in Philippine basic education: The case of Brigada Eskwela. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 7(2), 61-70
- Chall, J. S. (1983). *Stages of reading development*. McGraw-Hill.
- Chen, Y., Wong, S. W. L., & Lee, S. (2015). Effects of a community-based reading program on improving reading literacy skills and reading motivation in Hong Kong. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 38(1), 70-84

- Cho, Y. H., & Yoon, H. J. (2020). School-based reading intervention with family and community partnership. *Reading Improvement*, 57(2), 81-89
- Clary, E. G., Snyder, M., Ridge, R. D., Copeland, J., Stukas, A. A., Haugen, J., & Miene, P. (2015). Understanding and assessing the motivations of volunteers: A functional approach. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 74(6), 1516-1530
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*. Fourth edition. Washington DC: Sage. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7459/ept/43.2.05>
- Cockayne, N., Cacciattolo, M., & Willson, J. (2015). Social capital, social networks and literacy development in early childhood education: A review. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 40(3), 58-67
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). New York: Psychology Press.
- Cohen, D. K., Peurach, D. J., & Allen, J. P. (2014). Putting research in context: Understanding middle school mathematics teachers' use of research findings. *American Educational Research Journal*, 51(2), 418-449
- De Lara, L. V. (2016). Brigada Eskwela: Fostering social cohesiveness and reading skills development. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(1), 109-116
- Dlamini, B. B., & Dube, S. C. (2018). School maintenance as a catalyst for school effectiveness and learner performance in rural South Africa. *South African Journal of Education*, 38(2), 1-10
- Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., & Pachan, M. (2011). A meta-analysis of after-school programs that seek to promote personal and social skills in children and adolescents. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 45(3-4), 294-309.
- Ehri, L. C. (2005). Learning to read words: Theory, findings, and issues. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 9(2), 167-188.
- Elmore, R. F. (2000). *Building a new structure for school leadership*. The Albert Shanker Institute.

- Epstein, J. L. (2001). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Westview Press.
- Espiritu, M. R. (2018). Impact of Brigada Eskwela on school facilities and students' performance: A case study. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 5(2), 67-74
- Fisher, D., Frey, N., & Hattie, J. (2016). *Visible learning for literacy (Grades K-12): Implementing the practices that work best to accelerate student learning*. Thousand Oaks, CA :Corwin Literacy
- Gökçek, Tuba; Yilmaz, Aynur (2019). The Adaptation of the Pedagogical Knowledge and Skills Survey into Turkish: Validity and Reliability Study *Turkish Journal of Education*, v8 n1 p52-70 2019 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Pedagogical+skills+in+teaching+&id=EJ1301059>
- Harrington, M. M., & Sawyer, B. E. (2016). A community-based, multisite intervention for preschoolers at risk for reading difficulties. *Journal of Educational Research*, 109(4), 435-447
- Hiebert, E. H., & Reutzel, D. R. (2010). *Revisiting silent reading: New directions for teachers and researchers*. International Reading Association
- JASP. (n.d.). *A Fresh Way to do Statistics*. info@jasp-stats.org.
- Johnson, A. R., Anderko, A., & Van Slyke-Briggs, K. (2018). A collaborative approach to developing advanced reading skills in community college students. *Journal of College Reading and Learning*, 48(1), 26-42
- Karyono, T., Zain, A., & Damanik, D. (2020). Capacity-building and maintenance of schools in Indonesia. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 13(5)
- Kim, S. J., & Lee, S. K. (2015). The impact of community service on university students' attitudes towards social issues and civic engagement: Focused on the Community Service for Education in Korea. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 16(4), 585-596
- Kim, M. H., & Lee, H. (2016). The impact of a community-based program on improving advanced reading skills. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 60(3), 269-277
- Kim, J., & Choi, I. (2020). Empowering teachers to improve struggling readers' comprehension: A randomized controlled trial. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 55(1), 119-139

- Koenig, Thomas and Katie MacMillan (2004). Preconceptions and Expectations for Data Analysis Software in Qualitative Research. *The Wow Factor Social Science Computer Review*
- Kuby, P. B., Weber, L. K., & Larson, L. C. (2004). Community-wide literacy campaigns: Collaborating for change. *The Reading Teacher*, 58(6), 518-526
- Lee, K. N., Prakash, A., & Pomerantz, D. (2016). Shared accountability: A powerful tool for building trust in government. *World Resources Institute*
- Lee, S., & Kim, S. (2019). The effect of collaborative management on school maintenance week. *Sustainability*, 11(23), 6681
- Lee, S., & Kim, S. (2020). The effect of stakeholder involvement on collaborative management in school maintenance week. *Sustainability*, 12(16), 6551
- Lee, J. Y., & Koo, C. (2019). Understanding the factors affecting volunteers' intention to participate in community service for education in South Korea. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 64, 1-11
- Leithwood, K., & Jantzi, D. (2000). The effects of transformational leadership on organizational conditions and student engagement with school. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 38(2), 112-129.
- Liu, Y., Li, X., & Zhang, W. (2017). The impact of community-based afterschool programs on students' reading achievement. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 82, 228-235
- Lotich, Patricia (2011). What is the Purpose and Advantages of the Focus Group Interviews?. *Social Media Today*. socialmediatoday.com.
- Muthukrishna, N., Frey, A., & King, E. (2019). Empowering parents to promote children's literacy: A randomized evaluation of a home-based intervention in Sri Lanka. *World Development*, 115, 305-321
- National Conference on Citizenship. (2022). Social capital research. Retrieved from <https://www.ncoc.org/research/social-capital-research/>
- National Institute of Child Health and Human Development. (2000). Report of the National Reading Panel. *National Institutes of Health*
- Nind, Melanie (2020). A New Application for the Concept of Pedagogical Content

Knowledge: Teaching Advanced Social Science Research Methods Oxford Review
of Education, v46 n2 p185-201 2020
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2019.1644996>

Peace Corps. (2022). About. Retrieved from <https://www.peacecorps.gov/about/>

Peace Corps. (2022). About. Retrieved from <https://www.peacecorps.gov/about/>

Peñaranda, C., Montalbo, M. L., & Lañada, J. C. (2017). The effects of Brigada Eskwela on social cohesiveness and parental involvement in reading. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(16), 90-95

Penuel, W. R., Fishman, B. J., Cheng, B. H., & Sabelli, N. (2011). Organizing research and development at the intersection of learning, implementation, and design. *Educational Researcher*, 40(7), 331-337

Penuel, W. R., Allen, A. R., Coburn, C. E., & Farrell, C. (2015). Conceptualizing and advancing teacher professional development for social networked learning. *Educational Researcher*, 44(5), 263-271

Pronovost, P. J., Berenholtz, S. M., Goeschel, C. A., & Needham, D. M. (2011). Creating high reliability in health care organizations. *Health Services Research*, 46(6pt1), 1599-1617

Putnam, R. D. (2000). *Bowling alone: The collapse and revival of American community*. Simon and Schuster

Raosoft. (n.d.). Raosoft Sample Size Calculator.
<http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>.

Rappaport, J. (1987). Terms of empowerment/exemplars of prevention: Toward a theory for community psychology. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 15(2), 121-148.

Rebamonte, R. (2019). Parents' participation in Brigada Eskwela and learners' reading performance. *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 11(3), 166-172

Rutherford, D. L., & Wilkins, D. A. (2016). The impact of school maintenance week. *Facilities*, 34(5/6), 325-339

Senechal, M., & LeFevre, J. A. (2018). Community literacy program effects on vocabulary and comprehension skills of at-risk kindergarten children. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(5), 634-647

Serdoncillo, L. T., & Gadioma, D. D. (2020). *Brigada Eskwela: Enhancing community participation in Philippine education*

- Shanahan, T., Callison, K., Carriere, C., Duke, N. K., Pearson, P. D., Schatschneider, C., & Torgesen, J. (2010). Improving reading comprehension in kindergarten through 3rd grade: IES practice guide. Institute of Education Sciences.
- Smith, J. K., & Jones, T. (2017). The impact of community-based reading programs on advanced reading skills. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 33(2), 113-128
- Song, H. J., & Lee, M. H. (2018). Effects of volunteering at schools on the self-esteem and social skills of volunteers: A case study of Community Service for Education in South Korea. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 23(4), 422-433
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (20). Using multivariate statistics (5. ed., Pearson international ed., [Nachdr.]). Pearson Allyn and Bacon.
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2001). How to differentiate instruction in mixed-ability classrooms (2nd ed.). Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Tumwebaze, J. K., & Kikomoba, J. B. (2019). Community involvement in school maintenance and academic performance in primary schools in Kiboga District, Uganda. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(8), 135-142
- United Nations Volunteers. (2022). About us. Retrieved from <https://www.unv.org/about-us>
- United Nations Volunteers. (2022). About us. Retrieved from <https://www.unv.org/about-us>
- Wei, C. L., Chen, J., & Duan, X. (2015). Family and community involvement and intermediate reading achievement: A path analysis. *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, 25(1), 83-99
- Williams, T., & McLaughlin, T. F. (2016). The effectiveness of a family-school-community shared accountability approach to student achievement. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 109(2), 187-200
- Wilson, J. (2000). Volunteering. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 26, 215-240.
- Yohannes, A., Alemayehu, W., & Mesfin, A. (2018). The effect of community involvement in school governance on the quality of education in primary schools of Tigray region, Ethiopia
- Zimmerman, M. A. (2000). Empowerment theory: Psychological, organizational and community levels of analysis. In J. Rappaport & E. Seidman (Eds.), *Handbook of community psychology* (pp. 43-63). Springer.